

Phytochemical studies of marine green algae *Boodlea composita* from Ukha, west coast of India

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Abstract : Phytochemical investigation of marine green algae *Boodlea compositae* collected from the Ukha, west coast of India led to the isolation and identification of 22 constituents : β -sitosterol, loliolide and 13²-hydroxy-(13²-S)-phaeophytin-a being isolated by column chromatography whereas six fatty acids and 13 additional sterols were identified by GC-MS analysis. Characterization of β -sitosterol, loliolide and 13²-hydroxy-(13²-S)-phaeophytin-a was achieved by NMR spectroscopic data and comparison with those reported in literatures.

Keywords : β -Sitosterol, loliolide, pheophytin-a, green algae, GC-mass, spectroscopic data.

Introduction

Marine macroalgae inhabited in different oceanic waters have been group into three classes : green (Chlorophytes), brown (Pheophytes) and red (Rhodophytes) algae. Numerous compounds including sterols¹, terpenes², phenols³, carotenoids⁴ and polysaccharides⁵ have been isolated from marine algae and investigated their biological significant. Some of the isolated algal metabolites were known to play a significant ecological role^{3,6}. Among the metabolites of marine algae, sterols constitute one of the most abundant metabolite and found in diverse structural features. Certain sterol showed biological properties including feeding deterrent⁶ and cytotoxicity activity⁷. Specifically, β -sitosterol showed a wide range of activity including apoptosis, cytotoxicity and immunomodulatory activity⁷⁻⁹.

Metabolite such as loliolide has been isolated mainly from terrestrial plants though limited report were available from marine sources primarily from red and brown algae^{10,11}. The pigments, pheophytin and their derivatives were isolated from various marine algae^{12,13}. Loliolide exhibited potent anti-repellent activity¹⁴ and inhibitory effects¹⁵, whereas, pheophytin-a and its

derivatives showed antinociceptive effect¹⁶ and antitumor activity¹⁷. Prior to this communication, loliolide was reported only from a green algae *Enteromorpha compressa*¹⁸. In this study, we report isolation of β -sitosterol, loliolide and 13²-hydroxy-(13²-S)-phaeophytin-a from the green alga *Bodlea composita* by column chromatography. The compounds have been characterized with the help of FT-IR, NMR and mass spectroscopic data. Additionally, we identified thirteen other sterols and six fatty acids from this alga by GC-MS analysis.

Results and discussion

Extract of marine green alga *B. composita* collected from Okha, Gujarat coast of India upon subjected to column chromatography led to the isolation of β -sitosterol (**1**), loliolide (**2**) and 13²-hydroxy-(13²-S)-phaeophytin-a (**3**) (Fig. 1). The identity of the compounds **1-3** were established by NMR spectroscopic data as well as comparison with literatures^{10,19,20}. IR spectrum of β -sitosterol showed absorption peak at 3300 cm⁻¹ assignable to O-H stretching frequency. The solution optical rotation of β -sitosterol (stigma-5-en-3 β -ol) in CHCl₃ showed $[\alpha]_D = -40.49^\circ$ comparable to the reported value of -30 to -40° . The other two con-

stituents isolated from this alga by column chromatography have been established as loliolide (2) and 13²-hydroxy-(13²-S)-phaeophytin-a (3). Loliolide (2) was obtained as colorless oil by column chromatography and showed IR absorption peaks at 1730 and 3462 cm⁻¹ assignable to C=O and OH stretching frequency.

Fig. 1. Structures of β -sitosterol (1), loliolide (2) and 13²-hydroxy-(13²-S)-phaeophytin-a (3).

¹³C NMR spectrum of 2 showed signal at δ 181.7 and 172.4 assignable to ketone (C-8) and quaternary carbon (C-6). ESI-MS of loliolide showed intense peak at m/z 197.1322 (M+H)⁺ and at m/z 219.1048 [M+Na]⁺. 13²-Hydroxy-(13²-S)-phaeophytin-a (3) was separated as green pigment by column chromatography. ¹³C NMR spectrum of 3 showed signal at δ 88.9 assignable to the oxygenated carbon (C-13²). Spectrum displayed 55 distinct signals and data are well matched with literature²⁰.

Although compounds 1-3 isolated from *B. compositae* have already been reported in literature, they are being reported for the first time from this species as a new source. Further, identification of other sterols component present in the alga has been carried out by GC-MS analysis after silylation with silylating agent providing 13 other sterol constituents (Table 1). GC analysis showed stigma-5-en-3 β -ol (53.4%) was the major constituent present in the alga.

The sterols, cholest-5-en-3 β -ol (15.9%) and 24-

Table 1. Sterol components identified for *Boodlea composita* by GC-MS

Systematic name of sterols	R.T. ^a	Relative abundant (%) area ^b	Mol. wt. (O-TMS derivative)
Cholest-7,22-diene-3 β -ol	36.094	1.16	456
Cholest-7,22-diene-3 α -ol	36.142	0.5	456
Cholest-5-en-3 β -ol	36.505	15.98	458
3 β ,22E-Ergosta-7,22-dien-3-ol	36.951	2.58	470
3 β ,5 α -Cholest-7-ene-3-ol	37.098	0.64	458
3 β ,5 β -Cholest-7-en-3-ol	37.238	0.6	458
24-Methylene cholesterol	37.544	14.13	470
Ergost-7-en-3 β -ol	37.603	2.45	472
Stigma-5,22-dien-3 β -ol	37.815	0.67	484
Stigma-5,22-dien-3 α -ol	37.904	0.54	484
Stigma-7,22-dien-3 α -ol	38.215	2.74	484
Stigma-5-en-3 α -ol	38.331	1.99	414 ^c
Stigma-5-en-3 β -ol	38.51	53.45	486
Stigma-7,22-dien-3 α -ol	38.653	2.18	484

^aRetention time of silylated sterols, ^bquantification of silylated sterols based on the area of the GC peak, ^cunconverted.

methylene cholesterol (14.1%) were other sterols present in significant concentration (Table 1). The fatty acid constituent of the alga was also established by methylation of the isolated fatty acid mixture followed by GC-MS analysis. The fatty acids constituents identified comprise of myristic acid, palmitic acid, palmitoleic acid, stearic acid, vaccenic acid and elaidic/oleic acid.

Experimental

General remarks : The green algae *Boodlea composita* was collected from Okha, Gujarat coast during low tide. Solvents used for extraction and purification were of analytical grade and used as received. Infrared spectra were recorded using a diffused reflection spectroscopy (DRS) assembly on a Shimadzu-8201PC spectrometer. Analysis of sterol silyl ethers and fatty acids were carried out on a Shimadzu GC-MS QP2010 system using capillary column XTI-5.

Structural assignments were based on mass spectrometric fragmentations pattern and reference library²¹. Sterols were identified as their trimethyl silyl ether

(TMS ether). ESI-MS analysis was performed using QTOF Applied Biosystems mass spectrometer. NMR spectra were recorded on a Bruker Avance 300 MHz spectrometer at 300.13 (^1H) and 75.47 MHz (^{13}C) with SiMe_4 as internal reference and coupling constants were given in Hertz. Silylating agent (BSA+TMSCL+TMSI) was received from Sigma Aldrich Pvt. Ltd., India. Column chromatography was performed on silica gel (60–120 mesh, Merck, Darmstadt, Germany or SRL, Pvt. Ltd., India) or Shephadex LH-20.

Extraction and isolation of β -sitosterol (1), loliolide (2) and 13²-hydroxy-(13²-S)-phaeophytin-a (3) : Freshly collected alga was extracted with CHCl_3 : methanol (1 : 1) then rotary evaporated. Crude extract (2 g) was dissolved in minimum amount of CHCl_3 : methanol (1 : 1) then loaded in a pre-equilibrated Sephadex LH-20 column and elute with CHCl_3 : methanol (1 : 1) giving three major fractions (fraction-1 to fraction-3). Repeated column chromatography over silica gel column followed by Sephadex LH-20 led to isolation of **3** (15 mg) from fraction-1, **1** (42 mg) along with mixture of sterols and fatty acids from fraction-2 and **2** (5 mg) from fraction-3.

β -Sitosterol (1) : Colourless crystals. IR (neat) : 3350 (OH); m/z (ESI) : 415.2567 ($\text{M}+\text{H}^+$); ^1H NMR (CDCl_3 , 300 MHz) : 0.69 (3H, m), 0.81–1.09 (17H, m), 1.34 (4H, m), 1.49–1.53 (5H, m), 1.84–1.96 (11H, m), 2.03–2.20 (3H, m), 2.24 (2H, m), 2.34 (2H, m), 3.54 (1H, m), 5.35 (1H, d $J=3$); ^{13}C NMR (CDCl_3 , 75 MHz) : δ 11.84 (C-29), 12.30 (C-24), 19.0 (C-28), 19.2 (C-19), 19.6 (C-27), 19.58 (C-26), 21.0 (C-11), 23.0 (C-23), 26.3 (C-15), 26.3 (C-21), 28.2 (C-16), 28.9 (C-25), 31.5 (C-2), 31.6 (C-7), 31.6 (C-8), 33.9 (C-20), 36.2 (18), 36.5 (C-10), 37.25 (C-1), 39.7 (C-12), 42.3 (C-4), 42.30 (C-13), 46.0 (C-22), 50.13 (C-9), 56.0 (C-17), 56.7 (C-14), 71.8 (C-3), 121.7 (C-6), 140.7 (C-5). Specific rotation : -40.499° (Found); -30 to -40° (Reported).

Loliolide (2) : Physical state; colourless liquid. IR (neat) : 1730 (C=O), 3462 (O-H); m/z (ESI) : 197.1322 ($\text{M}+\text{H}^+$), 219.1048 ($\text{M}+\text{Na}^+$), 172.0867; ^1H NMR (CDCl_3 , 300 MHz) : 1.29 (3H, s, 1 β -Me), 1.62–1.48 (5H, m, 4 α , 2 α -H and 1 α -Me), 1.94 (3H, s, 5-Me),

2.02 (1H, m, 2 β -H), 2.49 (1H, m, 4 β -H), 4.34 (1H, s, H-3), 5.82 (1H, s, H-7); ^{13}C NMR (CDCl_3 , 75 MHz) : δ 26.49 (C-10), 27.00 (C-9), 30.64 (C-11), 35.89 (C-1), 45.62 (C-4), 47.32 (C-2), 66.86 (C-3), 99.9 (C-5), 112.95 (C-7), 172.4 (C-8), 182.1 (C-6).

13²-Hydroxy-(13²-S)-phaeophytin-a (3) : Blackish green powder. UV (methanol) (nm) : 203, 275, 404, 502, 532, 665; IR (cm^{-1}) : 1620, 1707, 1741, 2858, 2926, 2954, 3750; ^1H NMR (CDCl_3 , 300 MHz) : 0.80–0.89 (18H, m), 0.99–1.02 (6H, m), 1.13–1.16 (4H, m), 1.68–1.71 (5H, m), 1.87–1.95 (3H, m), 2.04–2.12 (3H, m), 2.30–2.36 (4H, m), 2.83 (3H, m), 3.25 (3H, m), 3.44 (3H, m), 3.63 (3H, m), 3.75 (3H, m), 4.16 (1H, m), 4.49–4.58 (3H, m), 5.20 (1H, m), 5.39 (4H, br s), 5.59 (1H, s), 6.26 (2H, dd, $J=18, 36$), 8.03 (1H, s), 8.76 (1H, s), 9.45 (1H, s), 9.61 (1H, s); ^{13}C NMR (75 MHz) : (Prophyrin) δ 11.2 (C-7¹), 12.1 (C-2¹), 12.2 (C-12¹), 16.3 (C-8²), 19.4 (C-8¹), 25.6 (C-16), 29.3 (C-17¹), 29.6 (C-17²), 49.9 (C-18), 51.8 (C-17), 53.2 (C-13⁴), 88.9 (C-13²), 93.6 (C-20), 97.1 (C-5), 104.2 (C-10), 107.5 (C-15), 122.8 (C-3²), 126.8 (C-3¹), 129.1 (C-13), 129.4 (C-12), 131.7 (C-2), 136.1 (C-7), 136.2 (C-3), 136.5 (C-4), 137.8 (C-11), 142.0 (C-1), 145.2 (C-8), 149.7 (C-14), 151.0 (C-9), 155.3 (C-6), 162.4 (C-16), 172.3 (C-13³), 172.7 (C-19), 173.5 (C-17³), 192.04 (C-13¹); (phytyl group) : 17.2 (C-20'), 19.6 (C-19'), 19.7 (C-18'), 22.6 (C-17'), 22.7 (C-16'), 24.4 (C-9'), 24.7 (C-13'), 25.0 (C-5'), 27.9 (C-15'), 31.5 (C-11'), 32.6 (C-7'), 32.7 (C-17'), 36.6 (C-6'), 37.2 (C-12'), 37.3 (C-8'), 39.3 (C-14'), 39.8 (C-4'), 61.25 (C-1'), 117.8 (C-2'), 142.7 (C-3').

Silylation of sterols : Saponification of sterols was carried out following a published procedure²². Algal extract (1 g) was dissolved in saponification agent prepared by dissolving 0.6 mL of 33% KOH in 10 mL of methanol. The mixture was stirred for 12 h at 60–70° C. After that 5 mL of hexane and water were added then centrifuged, the hexane layer was separated and then dried, the residue was dissolved in silylating agent (BSA+TMSCL+TMSI) and incubated in a dry reaction tube under nitrogen at 60 °C for 2 h. After which 5 mL of hexane and water was added then the hexane layer was submitted for GC/MS analysis.

Methylation of fatty acids : Fatty acids were iso-

lated by column chromatography over silica gel column with petroleum ether/ethyl acetate solvent mixture as eluent. Isolated fatty acids 5 mg was dissolved in 5 mL of methanol and 0.7 mL of 10 N KOH was added, then the mixture was incubated at 60° C for 2 h. After which, 0.58 mL of 24 N H₂SO₄ was added and incubated at 60° C for 2 h. To this mixture 3 mL of hexane and water was added then centrifuged, the hexane layer was subjected to GC/MS analysis.

Supplementary material

Copies of ¹H and ¹³C NMR spectra of compounds 1-3. Result of GC-MS analysis for crude extract.

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